

BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE CAPABILITIES' EFFECTS ON PERFORMANCE IN A COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT STUDYING ON-SITE AT THE TOUCHES FOUNDATION FOR ART AND INNOVATION

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Abstract

This study aims to determine how the touches Foundation for Innovation and the Arts' competitive performance was impacted by its business intelligence capabilities. All 63 members of the touches Foundation for Innovation and the Arts make up the study community. The study's methodology was based on a scoring descriptive approach that identified two aspects-the first of which was business intelligence capabilities-and three other dimensions. These are (business intelligence techniques, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture) and competitive performance after four dimensions (cost, quality, flexibility, access) According to the study's findings, the Touches Foundation for Innovation and the Arts employees had an average degree of business intelligence across all of its aspects. The study's findings also indicated that the Touches Foundation for Innovation and the Arts employees' level of performance in a competitive environment was average additionally, the findings of the regression equation have demonstrated that there are statistically significant disparities between competitive performance and business intelligence skills across all dimensions. The study's conclusion included a number of recommendations, including educating the company's leadership and workers about the importance of acquiring business intelligence skills in order to enhance the operation of the company and take advantage of future business prospects.

Keywords: Business Intelligence Abilities, Competitive Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Business companies work hard to implement contemporary technology and use it to further their own objectives, particularly those pertaining to the administrative sector, in order to achieve excellence, develop a competitive advantage, connect with as many target customers as possible, and offer cutting- edge goods and services Because of this, businesses have put a lot of effort into developing efficient technologies that can make the best use of their own resources and capabilities, utilizing business intelligence techniques to establish efficient performance management channels and information that fosters communication between employees and stakeholders in general in order to significantly affect the Organization's competitive performance with a view to excellence and maintaining competitive advantage On the other side, there is a lot of competition in the world today, especially now that the idea of globalization has become so well- known In order to achieve greatness, firms must adopt administrative techniques and foster a culture of business intelligence Business intelligence capabilities produce high- quality information that aids a corporation in identifying environmental concerns and possibilities for investment identifying and seizing opportunities to outperform competitors and boost their competitive performance Particularly in light of

market expansion and the rise of globalization, which have increased pressure on businesses to raise the caliber of their output the quest of continuity and adaptation to the requirements of the environment, both internal and external Given the significance of the link between competitive performance and business intelligence skills, In an effort to leverage technology advancement and the advancement of business intelligence capabilities while also identifying their influence on competitive performance. These crucial management factors and how they are used in a setting that deals with creativity and the arts are the subjects of this study

Study problem

Businesses nowadays must the ther greatest resources and competencies to meet the sanous problems posed by the external meronment's quick changes particularly this industry's major evolution in information technology maintaining them and implementing contemporary management ideas that help firms become more able to react to their external environments and steadily improve their strategic performance through the development of business intelligence skillsOne of the modern management ideas forced by the competitive work enveonment is the subject of competitive performance which is the constant strengthening of its strategic performance through the development of business intelligence capabilitest aidh and enables the Organization to utilize its assets and capabilities to the fullest extent possible, quaranteeing that it can maintain its competitive advantage in the face of quick changes and advancements in the business environment.Based on the foregoing the issue with the study can be summed up as follows: What effect do business intelligence capabilities in a setting that involves creativity and the arts have on competitive performance

Study's questions:

- 1) What level of availability of business intelligence capabilities in its following dimensions): Business Intelligence Techniques, Business Intelligence Structuring, Business Intelligence Culture) At the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Arts from the point of view of workers?
- 2) What is the level of availability of competitive performance in the following dimensions: (cost, quality, flexibility, access) At the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Arts from the point of view of workers?

Study's aims:

The study aims to recognize the impact of business intelligence capabilities in competitive performance

At the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Arts and it has the following set of aims:

- 1) Developing a cognitive framework for study variables of business intelligence capabilities Competitive performance and clarification of these concepts in their different dimensions to form a clear picture of them.
- 2) Recognize the level of availability of dimensions of business intelligence capabilities):Business Intelligence Techniques, Business Intelligence Structuring,

- Business Intelligence Culture) At the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Art.
- 3) Recognize the level of availability of competitive performance: (cost, quality, flexibility, access) At the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Arts.
 - 4) Analyze the impact of business intelligence capabilities in their dimensions):)Business Intelligence Techniques, Business Intelligence Structuring, Business Intelligence Culture)in competitive performance in the company of the Foundation lamasat for Creativity and Arts.

The importance of the study:

The importance of this study comes from the nature of the variables it address, where the concept of business intelligence capabilities is one of the contemporary variables That allows the Organization to keep abreast of technological developments and technology of information and data management of importance In a dynamic environment, enhancing and improving the competitive performance of systems beyond competitors are key issues that the organization seeks to achieve To achieve the largest possible market share by providing products and services that exceed customers' expectations, the importance of the study can be clarified by two sides as follows:

Scientific important:

The academic importance of this study is as follows:

- 1) Provide an explanation of the concepts of study variables and dimensions by reviewing past literature and researches.
- 2) Providing an integrated theoretical framework based on the efforts of previous researchers in addition to the researcher's perspective on the concepts and society of the study.
- 3) The importance of the concept of both business intelligence and competitive performance in inheritance thinking is an important source of the organization's continuity.

The applied importance:

The applicable importance of this study is to:

- 1) Provide a set of recommendations to help decision makers at the Foundation understand the concepts related to study variables and their application.
- 2) The importance of the institution as it meets the needs of the category seeking to acquire is innovative and new.

In order to achieve the purpose of the present study and reach its objective, the researcher has developed a study model and shape (1) shows the study model and its dimension.

Figure (1): Study's Model

Study hypotheses:

These studies based on a group of hypotheses , that emerged from problem of studying and other elements , it's possible to highlight the relationship between studying through the main null hypothesis : There is no effect statistically significant : according to prescription respondents for business intelligence capability for its distance (Technic (0.05<a) the significance level the business of intelligence Structure of business intelligence, and culture of business intelligence) combined in competitive performance (cost, quality, flexibility, access) in the institution.

Procedural definitions:

In the light of the review of the various definitions dealt with in previous literature reviews, these procedures can be defined as follows:

Independent Variable: Business Intelligence Capabilities The enterprise's ability to exploit technological resources in collecting and analyzing data from the internal and external environment and to access any information that helps the Department in making decisions about the work of the Organization and building a culture based on the intensive application of technological resources

- 1) Business Intelligence Technologies: the methods and technological tools used by the institution company with the aim of providing new products and services and maintaining their position in the market.
- 2) Business intelligence structure: represents the institution's business intelligence structure by determining the sequence and flow of functions related to business intelligence and innovation.
- 3) Business Intelligence Culture: Values, Habits and Practices of the institution's Work Environment Based on the Technological Exploitation of All Aspects of its Work.

Affiliate Variable: Competitive performance

The results of the institution's business that can be achieved through the resources and capabilities available in the organization that help in reaching the distinctive competitive performance.

- 1) Cost: The value the enterprise uses to produce goods and services whether it is material value, effort or time drain lost opportunities
- 2) Quality: Enterprise's commitment to provide goods and services to customers according to standards that make the product flawless.
- 3) Flexibility: The ability of "Lamasat for Creativity and Arts" institution to continuously change its internal processes in order to provide services that consistently meet the needs of its clients.
- 4) Accessibility: The potential of "Lamasat for Creativity and Arts" institution to effectively and efficiently achieve its goals and aspirations within the available resources and capabilities, deliver products to its clients within the agreed-upon time frame.

Introduction:

Because of how quickly and dynamically business is changing nowadays it is essential for enforcement organizations to be up to date on all changes and new technology advances in order to take the required precautions enhancing their ability to develop and increase their competitive performance by recognizing market charges and changing client preferences (Nashiruddin, 2018) By using business intelligence systems, the Organization will be better equipped to carry out its operations and meet its goals in a time and cost efficient manner Since business intelligence systems combine technical expertise with technological infrastructure and organizational expertise with support from senior management to succeed above their rivals. It does this by gathering, storing and analyzing internal and external data for use in decision making giving the Organization an edge over its rivals (Batra, 2018)

Business intelligence capabilities:

Business intelligence can be thought of as the process by which firms turn data into information and use that information to make decisions (Ranjan, 2009) By gathering information on the Organization's activities across a variety of domains, storing it in specialized databases, analyzing it, and utilising the results (Good. 2016), Business intelligence is a method that describes how an organization generates usable information some people saw it as both practical and productive, The term "product" refers to data that aids an organization in anticipating the actions of clients vendors rival businesses, markets, and consumers of their goods and services. The aim is to empower individuals to make wise choices when interacting with any of these actors (Casero & Coelho, 2019) Others believed it was meant to evaluate the Organization's performance and success not just to aid in decision making (Luki et al. 2016).

Organizational capabilities such as organizational structure and regulatory policies, are defined as all tools, instruments. activities, and requirements that assist the Organization in achieving its goals Business intelligence capabilities fall under this category, and the organization's capacity to modify its strategies in response to outside changes Others employed additional elements, such as the business intelligence culture (Skyrios et al. 2016) or the business intelligence structure (Labour, 2018), in addition to the capability of its human resources in terms of knowledge, skills, and experience (AbouAssi and loe, 2017)

In addition to the capacity of its human resources of knowledge, skills and experience (Aboules and Joe 2017 others used other factors such as the business intelligence culture (kyrios et al. 2016) or the business intelligence structure Qabar 2018) Business

The importance of business intelligence capabilities

Organizations are actively seeking to own business intelligence applications, as it is considered a strategic tool used by managers to set organization priorities, improve management of decisions and processes, and support the achievement of strategic goals (Audzeyeva & Hudson, 2016). Business intelligence capabilities provide the organization with the ability to analyze and measure and thus help improve the control management system in organizations, their level of performance, and the provision of necessary information that helps managers make decisions (Banerjee & Mishra, 2017). It also provides the organization with data processing capabilities. And management, providing data analytics and presenting it to decision makers in a timely manner (Veramisti et al., 2020). It also helps organizations gain competitive advantage (Božič & Dimovski, 2019). It also improves customer satisfaction, enables the organization to recognize changes in customer preferences, improves organizational and strategic performance, increases the efficiency of its operations, and enables the organization to identify opportunities and threats early (Olexová, 2014). These capabilities also create the ability to manage performance indicators, analysis and forecasting, as the business intelligence system can integrate and process big data, and support many uses (Radenković et al., 2018).

Dimensions of business intelligence capabilities

The researchers used a set of different dimensions in their various studies, and due to the nature of the research and the nature of its society, the following dimensions were chosen: business intelligence techniques, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture, based on the study of Caseiro and Coelho (2019), Batra (2018) and Hawajra (2018). Business intelligence techniques

By utilizing the technical applications offered by the system and storing them in organizational memory, the business intelligence system gives the Organization the technological and organizational capabilities to benefit from the enormous amounts of data from various internal and external sources (IK et al. 2011) According to Gaardboe et al's 2017 analysis BAC has four fundamental capabilities: first, it has an organizational memory that keeps information organized so that it may be accessed and used in the future. Second information integration, which demonstrates the system's capacity to connect structured and unstructured data from many sources. The third type of them creates new perceptions using information to support decision makers in the short or long term. They then use the facts to support those beliefs The last step is information presentation which refers to providing consumers with material in a way that is understandable.

Business intelligence structure

The majority of the Department's literature concurred that the organizational structure, which typically had three levels strategic, tactical and operational, explained the roles and responsibilities of the organizational units and sections As a result the organizational structure used to deploy the business intelligence system functions through the interdependence of several management levels in order to make decisions about clients, rivals, and other stakeholders, the various functions share these degrees of information and expertise (Rud. 2009)

As a result, the organizational structure and the business intelligence structure must match and experts at various administrative levels should be able to use the system Encourage employees to embrace the change that comes with the system's implementation, keeping in mind the availability of control systems to assure the system's successful deployment. Business intelligence culture

The organizational culture serves as a guide for how employees behave within the company, including how they use technology to further the company's objectives (Mardiana et al. 2018) Therefore, it is imperative that the Organization work to ensure that its organizational culture and business intelligence technology are compatible As a result beneficiaries will be encouraged to provide information workers will feel more confident, and their relationships will strengthen This is necessary for business intelligence to succeed and for the organization to fulfill its objectives (Cekuls, 2015)

Competitive performance

According to researchers performance is defined as what a person or organization accomplishes in a specific area to produce a specific result (Neely 2002) emphasizes efficiency and efficiency, which are both defined as using the fewest resources necessary to achieve the intended goals. Second, the organization's effectiveness displays its capacity to accomplish its goals (Samsonowa 2012). Therefore, the ability of the Organization to accomplish its goals while using the least amount of resources is related to its performance.

Competition performance shows how well an organization performs in comparison to its rivals and how it stands out from the other competition organizations (Gebra et al, 2009). Additionally, they demonstrate the Organization's competitive advantages in delivering high-quality goods quickly in response to market demands based on innovation in both processes and goods (Mandi, 2005).

According to some scholars, the phrases competitive performance and competitive advantage are theoretically equivalent because the Organization's remarkable and sustainable performance results from a sustainable competitive advantage. The Organization must have a competitive advantage in order to achieve competitive performance (Sigalas et al. 2013).

Importance of competitive performance

Competitive performance is quite important in many areas, according to earlier studies. It favors gaining a competitive edge, growing the consumer base, raising pricing and fostering more brand loyalty (Wu & Chiu 2015). It also contributes to the Organization's ability to stand out from its rivals and achieve excellence in organizational performance. Additionally, it aids the organization in adding value to that it may increase revenues and safeguard its market share (Ibrahim and Huan, 2017).

Linking the value of competitive performance to the organization's competitive edge in the creation of new products and services enlarges the market share and develops a variety of client-satisfying distribution channels, putting an emphasis on the application of contemporary technology to lower product prices and create a solid financial position for the firm (Gibra et al. 2009). Competitive advantage is crucial for establishing competitive performance because it allows an organization to stand out from its rivals and accomplish its strategic goals (Break 2019).

Dimensions of competitive performance

In their various studies, researchers have employed a range of different dimensions. The following dimensions have been selected based on the nature of the research and the society it is conducted in. Based on research by Alywi (2016) and (2019), Shite et al (2016), Subrahmaniam & Azad, this section discusses business intelligence approaches, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture.

Cost

Cost refers to the Organization's capacity to offer its goods at a lower price than those of its rivals, provided that this does not compromise the goods quality (Aliw 2016). This is done by using a cost leading approach that enables the company to sell its goods for less money particularly if rival companies enter the market and take control of it (Subrahmaniam & Azad. 2019). The organization is always working to keep its position as a cost leader in order to attain the advantage of price excellence, it necessitates a rigorous examination of all cost components and the ability to sell its product for less than rivals (Shalab, 2018)

Quality

A group of qualities that a firm exhibits in its goods or services are referred to as quality in order to outperform rivals at meeting client wants, As a result client expectations and requirements are fulfilled (Evans, 2008) According to some, the foundation of quality is to add value for customers and raise their level of happiness (Shalabi, 2018) Additionally, it suggest that the items delivered to customers have a low rate of production flaws (Awwad, 2011 The Organization's pursuit of a feasible plan will set it apart from competitors and highlight its distinctive qualities. By offering items and services that are challenging to duplicate and delivering orders on time. As a result, the Organization must possess a specific set of traits, competencies, and high efficiency. Continuously work to meet the demands and preferences of the customer while making wise use of the available resources (Alwi, 2016).

Flexibility

The topic of flexibility has been covered in administrative literature in several situations. The majority of people concur that they demonstrate the capacity to quickly adapt to all new developments, attitudes, and environmental changes and to make accommodations that depart from conventional thought patterns (Burget et al., 2017).Flexibility in terms of competitive performance has been demonstrated by the Organization's capacity to alter its strategic course,Its tactical and general preparedness for dealing with upcoming events (Shalabi, 2018),It also indicates the organization's capacity to foresee and predict any change that might happen and endanger the organization. It benefits from having the ability to strategically adapt to various environments and shifting external environmental elements (Sihite et al., 2016), Flexibility, then, is a measure of an organization's capacity to adjust to and continually prepare for a dynamic environment that is continuously changing. In order to ensure its continued existence, wealth, and accomplishment of its strategic aim

Access

Customers are given access to product delivery within a predetermined window of time without experiencing any delays (Lim & Trimi, 2014). Due to the tight competition with competitors, the organization must work to develop its operations. They must also conduct research into the present and foreseeable needs of their clientele and examine their patterns of behavior and purchasing power. Their time to shine and build market share by pleasing them and keeping them for as long as feasible (Sigalas & Economou, 2013). A study named "The Intermediate

Role of Business Intelligence Capabilities between Organizational Leadership and Strategic Success at Jordanian Government Universities" was conducted by Hajra (2018).

The study's objective was to determine how business intelligence capabilities at Jordanian government universities affected the relationship between organizational leadership and strategic performance. Using an analytical descriptive technique, the researcher developed identification as a tool for the study and discovered a statistically significant impact of business intelligence capabilities on strategic success; Business intelligence capabilities play an intermediary role in the relationship between organizational leadership and strategic success, according to the study's findings and the impact of organizational leadership on that achievement. The Mesopotamia of Business Intelligence Systems in the Relationship between Organizational Immunity and the Success of Financial Decisions, by Hassan (2019), was applied to enterprises in the Gazan food industry. The study's goal was to pinpoint business intelligence systems' intermediary function in the connection between organizational resilience and the success of financial decisions, The study discovered that the effectiveness of business intelligence systems as a middleman has had an impact on the relationship between organizational resilience and the success of financial decisions through the establishment of Istvone as a tool for study, Business intelligence system implementation has also been at a high level.

Mohamed (2020) research: Samsung case study, Algeria, impact of marketing innovation on the competitive performance of the production firm in the sector of smartphones.

The analytical descriptive approach was employed in the study's analysis of the effect of marketing innovation on competitive performance; the study discovered a statistically significant positive association between the characteristics of marketing innovation and competitive performance through the establishment of Istvone as a tool for study. The study's findings also indicated a high degree of performance in competition. Samah (2020); Field study on clothing enterprises in Cairo Governorate, Egypt: Impact of marketing creativity on the Organization's Competitive Performance: The Modified Role of Environmental Uncertainty The goal of the study was to determine how altered environmental uncertainty affected the relationship between marketing creativity and competitive performance. The study discovered that marketing expertise has a statistically significant impact on enhancing competitive performance through the establishment of Istvone as a study aid. The research firms applied competitive performance at a moderate level.

English studies

A study (Cheng et al., 2020) entitled Facilitating speed of internationalization. The roles of business intelligence and organizational agency

The study's goal was to determine how business intelligence (data integration and analytical skills) affected how quickly businesses deployed abroad while operating under the modified influence of operational regulatory control and cultural distance. Through the creation of an identification as a study tool, the study employed the analytical descriptive approach. The study discovered that business information has an effect on quick deployment. There is a middle

variable in organizational agility.

Study (Jaklič et al., 2018) entitled the role of compatibility in predicting business intelligence and analyses use intentions Disclosure of the importance of compatibility in business intelligence's ability to anticipate company structure through the creation of István as a study tool, the study employed the analytical descriptive technique. According to the study's findings business intelligence tools helped organizations be more predictable, increasing organizational predictability was one of the key factors in choosing a business intelligence strategy.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The descriptive method of analysis was utilized in the study, allowing the researcher to get information directly from the study participants.

Study community

All 63 employees of a facility dedicated to innovation and the arts make up the study community. It was totally used as a study sample due to society's constraints.

Study tool

The study tool was an identification established with the use of various studies that were pertinent to the study's topic, where it was written by several specialists and confirmed via the use of reliable and consistent statistical processes.

Scale of study tool:

A pentaliter scale (1-5) has been utilized to quantify the study staff's reactions to the tool's vertebrae, with a substantial portion of the scale (which represents the weight (5)) signifying the response to the vertebrae Weight (4), medium and weight (3), low and weight (2), I disagree, and weight (1)), and the following equation has been used to explain the average level of study community members on each paragraph and in the entire area: The category has the following length: (the maximum of the alternative, the minimum of the alternative)/number of levels :

$$5.1 / 3 = 1.33$$

The three levels are:

Low: from (1), less than (2.34)

Average: from (2)

High: (2.34).34, which is less than 3.67 but greater than 3.67 to (5).

Statistical treatment:

To address the study's questions, appropriate statistical techniques have been applied. The regression test and mathematical averages and standard deviation have both been employed to address the study's major hypothesis. The following tables provide a description of these qualities in terms of frequency and percentage. The features of the study society have been based on a set of demographic and personal characteristics of the members of the study

community (gender, age, number of years of service).Gender

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Gender Variable

gender	frequency	percentage
males	45	%71.4
females	18	%28.6
sum	63	%100.0

With a rate of (9628.6). Table 1's data reveals that there were 18 females and 45 males (71.4% and 71.4%, respectively) living in the study community

Age

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Age Variable

age	percentage	frequency
Less than 35 years	%49.2	31
From 36 to less than 45 year	%41.3	26
46 and more	%9.5	6
sum	%100.0	63

Table 2 reveals that the working group (36-45) had the second-highest number of officials with 26 (41.39%), followed by the age group (under 35 years old), which had 31 officials and 49.2%. With 6 officials and 9.5%, the age group (under 45 years old) had the lowest representation of all the groupings.

Years of service

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Years of Service Variable

Years of experience	percentage	frequency
From 1 to 5	%23.8	15
From 5 to less than 10	%57.1	36
11 and more	%19.0	12
sum	%100.0	63

Table 3 demonstrates that the age range of 5 to 10 years old had the highest percentage of people with years of service in the school community, with 36 officials (57.1%), followed by 1 to 5 years of service, with 15 and 23.8%, and 11 and above with 12 officials and 19.0%

Key question 1: From a working perspective, what is the level of business intelligence capabilities in an organisation that engages with creativity and the arts in terms of the following aspects (business intelligence methodologies, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture)? The computational community and table 4 have been used to present results in order to address this query regarding the degree of application of business intelligence dimensions in the following dimensions (business intelligence techniques, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture) in an enterprise that touches innovation and art.

Table 4: Arithmetic Averages of Respondents' Perceptions of Business Intelligence Capability Dimensions

dimension		Arithmetic Average	Level Relative to Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	rank
1. Business Intelligence Techniques		3.46	Average	0.49	1
2. Business Intelligence Structure		3.26	Average	0.45	2
3. Business Intelligence Culture		3.31	Average	0.31	3
	Arithmetic Average of Strategic Thinking	3.34	Average		

The mathematical averages of researchers' perceptions of the dimensions of business intelligence

The dimensions were calculated between 3.2 and 3.46 on a five-year leker scale. The level of business intelligence was therefore ordinary. After the first level (business intelligence techniques), which scored an average of 3.46, there was a distance (business intelligence culture), which scored an average of 3.31, and then there was a distance (business intelligence structure). Which scored an average of 3.26. This shows that the company's employees do not use business intelligence capabilities in their work, which necessitates training and workshops that help increase workers' awareness of the value of using business intelligence in business management to take advantage of the environment, thereby helping to increase the company's

What level of competitive performance is available in a company that impacts creativity and the arts from a working perspective in terms of its dimensions (cost, quality, flexibility, access)? The computational community, rank, and table 5 present the results to address this query regarding the level of application of the dimensions of competitive performance in its dimensions (cost, quality, flexibility, and access) in a company that impacts creativity and art from a working point of view.

Table 5: Arithmetic Averages of Respondents' Perceptions of Competitive Performance Dimensions

Level Relative to Arithmetic Mean	rank	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic average	dimension	num
average	3	0.49	3.43	cost	1
average	2	0.45	3.44	quality	2
average	4	0.31	3.33	flexibility	3
average	1	0.31	3.47	access	
average			3.42	Average Arithmetic of Strategic Thinking	

Accounting averages for researchers' opinions of factors that influence competitive performance

The combined competitive performance variable had an average of 3.42 percent and a median range of 3.47.333 percent. According to the results in table 5. Performance in the competition

was on a modest level. The distance after arrival was first at an average level and an average of 3.47 percent, then a distance (quality) at an average level and an average of 3.44 percent, a distance (cost) at an average level and an average of 3.43 percent, a distance (flexibility) at an average level and an average of 3.33 percent. This shows that the company's personnel don't use business intelligence tools in their work, necessitating workshops and training that help. Intelligence culture) and its dimensions in achieving competitive performance in Lamasat Foundation for Creativity and Arts

The main hypothesis (H01): Researchers at an enterprise that deals with innovation and art do not have a statistically significant impact on their combined competitive performance (cost, quality, flexibility, and access). Table 6's information serves as an example of this:

Table 6: Multiple Regression Results Impact of the Analysis of Business IOs in their Dimensions (business intelligence methodologies, business intelligence structure, and business intelligence culture) with its dimensions in achieving competitive performance in an enterprise that affects innovation and art

Variance Analysis ANOVA			Model Summary		Dependent variable
Sig F* Significance Level	Degrees of Freedom	F Computed	R ² Coefficient of Determination	R Coefficient of Determination	Competitive Performance
0.003	3	5.349	.214	.461	
Coefficients					
Sig t* Significance Level	T Computed	Standard error	B	Independent Variables	
0.043*	.9112	0.060	.1250	Business Intelligence Techniques	
0.018*	1.329	0.080	0.107	Business Intelligence Structure	
.0350*	2.146	0.083	0.179	Business Intelligence Culture	

According to the association coefficient value (R) (0.461) of the dependent variable (competitive performance) and the independent variable (business intelligence skills), there is a meaningful and statistically significant relationship between them. In terms of the value (R) of the correlation coefficient (0.461), the results in table (00) likewise show a statistically significant relationship between the independent variable (worker intelligence skills) and the dependent variable (competing performance). According to the weighting (F) of the estimated value (5.349) at a significant level (005 degrees of warfare), the findings in table (00) also show a statistically significant effect for the independent variable (worker intelligence skills) in the dependent variable. The above table demonstrates that, in contrast to the increase in values (t) calculated from the scale to a moral significance (2.911, 1,329, 2.146), the consequences of the influence of workers' intelligence in its sub-schedules (business intelligence techniques, business intelligence, and worker intelligence culture) have a significant effect on the competitive performance dimension. We therefore reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative that there is a statistically significant influence on the combined level of business

intelligence capabilities following competitive success at an institution of artistic design.

Table 7

Significance Level	Computed (T) Value	R2 (Coefficient of Determination)	Order of Entry of Independent Variables in the Prediction Equation
*0.011	3.100	0.324	Business Intelligence Techniques
*0.041	2.234	0.432	Business Intelligence Structure
*0.021	2.214	0.558	Business Intelligence Culture

At the level of .05, the effect is statistically significant. Table 7's data demonstrates the sequence in which independent factors were introduced into the regression equation, which explained 32.4% of the variation in post-competitive performance following business intelligence. To improve the performance of the company and seize prospects for future employment, the study suggests raising employee and company leadership knowledge of the need to build business intelligence capabilities. The report suggests holding specialized training to help staff become more adept at determining what directly influences competitive performance and how possibilities for the business are taken advantage of

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